

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Akrawi****FIRST NAME: SINAN****PROGRAM CODE : DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2019 Student & Home edition on IOS)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **In many fields, important and significant research is increasingly published or archived online, so you can often do useful preliminary work with scholarly search engine such as...**

- Google search engine.
- Google scholar search engine.¹**
- Yahoo search engine.
- Wikipedia.

2. **Plagiarism is one of the dishonest practices many researchers make unintentionally, which of the following statements is mostly consistent with undeliberate plagiarism?**

¹ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 26.

- Students do not know they cheat when they put their names on a paper bought online.
 - You paraphrased a source and cited it, but in words different than the original source.
 - You cited a source but used its exact words without putting them in quotation marks.²**
 - You used ideas and methods from a source with successful citation.
3. **When you graphically present data as complex as in a paragraph. The simplest and most common are tables, bar charts, and line graphs, each of which has a distinctive effect, using a bar chart is to emphasize which of the following factors?**
- A bar chart emphasize comparison among different items.³**
 - Emphasize trends over time.
 - Achieves the effect you intend not coming first in your mind.
 - To emphasize specific values.
4. **A poster presentation is a practice that you summarize your research engaging it with your relevant proof, of the following considered as guideline for a poster presentation?**
- Leave graphs and table unexplained.
 - Highlighting the abstract below the summery.
 - Layer your argument in a four level details.

² Ibid, 51.

³ Ibid, 54-55.

- Restate your reasons and accumulate evidence under them.**⁴
5. **What is the type of indentation used in reference list entries according to Turabian rule of style?**
- Left indent controls the space between the paragraph and the left margin.
- Hanging indentation, the first line flushed to the left and the other lines the same of the paragraph.**⁵
- Right indent controls the space between the paragraph and the right margin and has a marker of its own.
- First line indent is used to indent the first line of a paragraph or of every paragraph.
6. **Which of the following software used for citation?**
- Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)
- Epi info.
- Endnote.**⁶
- Statistical Analysis System (SAS).
7. **Which one of the following is not a part of literature review?**

⁴ Ibid, 83.

⁵ Ibid, 130.

⁶ Bloomberg, Linda D. & Volpe, Marie. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 52.

- Definitions and/or explanations of the key terms used in the study that do not have a commonly understood meaning.**⁷
- Methodological Approach/Research Design.
- Theoretical/Conceptual Framework.
- Recommendations.
8. **The process involves asking a colleague to examine your field notes and then ask you questions that will help you examine your assumptions and/or consider alternative ways of looking at the data called?**
- Peer review.
- Peer debriefing.**⁸
- Credibility or validity.
- Dependability or reliability.
9. **The use of multiple methods and triangulation is critical in attempting to obtain an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under study, which of the following is not a data collection method?**
- Focus incident.**⁹
- Survey.
- Interview.
- Critical incident.

⁷ Ibid, 43-55.

⁸ Ibid, 78.

⁹ Ibid,82-85.

10. Which of the following is not a classification of analytic approaches by Crabtree and Miller (1992)?

- Quasi-statistical approaches
- Template approach.
- Data coding approach.**¹⁰
- Immersion approaches.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. California: Sage Publications, 2008.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and the University of Chicago Press. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

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¹⁰ Ibid, 98-99.